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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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The Light of Friendship

There was a season when my soul grew quiet,
and hope was as fragile as glass in my hands.

I had set my dreams adrift,
thinking they would never find the shore again.

And yet, you stood there.

No summons, no fanfare, just you,
a steady flame the night could not swallow.

When I could no longer pray for myself,
you prayed for me in secret.

When my voice faltered,
you spoke faith back into my bones,
You saw a small ember where I saw only ash,
and you breathed on it until it glowed.

You reminded me that strength doesn't vanish.
Sometimes, it only hides, waiting to be called.

Your friendship was never for show.
It bore the weight of storms without complaint.

No stage lights, no applause,
only the quiet truth of someone who stays.

Alhamdulillah for friends so rare,
whose loyalty speaks more loudly than words,
and whose kindness leaves a trail
that points the heart back to Him.